

A researcher's experience after receiving their first peer review often determines how they will view the process in years to come.

As time progresses, active researchers will start receiving requests to act as peer reviewers, and it is essential they have a positive role model.

How do you become a good reviewer? Apart from my top tips [here](#), clarity in [the role of peer review](#) and [what is expected of reviewers](#) should be well understood by the authors.

Here are the

5 main features reviewers analyse in their review report

a. NOVELTY

Is your study an original contribution to knowledge?

Have you properly explained the context for your research question, the rationale for the study, and the knowledge gap identified?

- ❖ Ensure that the title properly reflects the subject of the paper.

b. RELEVANCE

What is the possible impact of the work you conducted to the wider society?

Have you detailed possible applications outside of your narrow academic field?

- ❖ The abstract should provide an accessible summary of the paper and the keywords chosen strategically.

c. PRECISION

Is the research design sound, the study conducted according to ethical standards, and reporting compliant to the relevant guidelines?

Are there any major flaws, factual errors, or invalid arguments?

- ❖ Data interpretation should be accurate, and all relevant work fully addressed.

d. COMPLETENESS

Is the paper of an appropriate length? Have all questions posed been addressed?

Have you presented all the data necessary to substantiate any claims?

- ❖ Acknowledge all the limitations of your study, and contrast your findings to similar work in the field.

e. CONCISENESS AND STRUCTURE

Does the paper follow a clear and organized structure?

Are the correct references cited?

- ❖ Avoid excessive, limited, or biased citations.

Above all, a peer reviewer's job is to assess the manuscript in a **critical, informed, impartial, unbiased, clear, correct, and grounded** manner.

The first challenge was beaten—you produced a sound document that fits the scope of your target publication. You know the story you want to tell and who you want to hear it. Your manuscript is now available for peer review.

However, reviewers are not responsible for making decisions pertaining to manuscript publication. It is the journal's editor or members of the editorial board who consider the feedback provided by peer reviewers and use this information to arrive at a decision.

The 5 main outcomes of peer review are:

a. REJECT THE PAPER

The journal will not publish the paper or reconsider it even if the authors make major revisions. This is mostly due to:

- ➔ Bad writing: If the language, structure, or figures are so poor that the merit of the paper can't be assessed.
- ➔ The research topic is of little significance: Findings are incremental and do not significantly advance the field.
- ➔ The work is clearly part of a larger study (i.e., “salami slicing”).

b. REVISE AND RESUBMIT

The journal is willing to reconsider the paper in another round of decision making after the authors make major changes. These are necessary because:

- ➔ A clear hypothesis or research aim was not established or the goal of the research was overly ambitious and could not be achieved (i.e., “HARKING”).
- ➔ There are flaws in the procedures and/or analysis of the data, such as irreproducible methods, lack of clear control groups (i.e., “double-dipping”), or inappropriate/invalid statistics (i.e., “p-hacking”).

c. ACCEPT AFTER MAJOR REVISIONS

The journal will publish the paper provided the authors make the changes suggested by the reviewers and/or editors. The more common culprits are:

- ➔ The manuscript is incomplete or ignores other important work in the field (i.e., “cherry-picking”).
- ➔ The conclusions ignore large portions of the literature, were exaggerated, or the data do not support the conclusions.

d. ACCEPT WITH MINOR REVISIONS

This is typically the best outcome that authors should hope for.

The journal will publish the paper and asks the author to make small corrections, usually requests for clarification of existing text, addition of text to fill a gap in the paper, or additional experimental details.

e. ACCEPT WITHOUT ANY CHANGES

This type of decision outcome is rare, a unicorn 🦄.

The journal will publish the paper in its original form.

If your paper was accepted, congratulations!

For most of us, that happens only after a protracted process. Data from 2023 shows that Science accepts only 6% of the original research papers submitted, with 83% of submitted manuscripts being desk rejected during the initial screening stage. For PLOS One, both metrics were approximately 31% in the first semester of 2023.

So, how will you react to the editor's decision?

5 possible reactions to rejection after peer review:

a. THROW THE MANUSCRIPT AWAY AND FORGET ABOUT IT

Don't do this! All results are useful and informative, and you deserve to have a publication associated with your project.

If you have spent resources and time on the study, report it even if contains only negative results. Consider posting a preprint or submitting a detailed protocol.

b. APPEAL AGAINST THE DECISION

Email the editor with a reasoned and logical explanation of why you believe the decision was based on an unfair assessment of your paper, or the review process was flawed.

If possible, set up a meeting and be prepared to address address the points raised by the reviewer(s), highlighting how you could improve the manuscript to a sufficient level for reconsideration.

c. REFORMAT AND SUBMIT TO A DIFFERENT JOURNAL

While no two reviews are the same, some of the suggestions made by the original reviewers could improve the paper.

If the journal is part of a transfer program, the editor may refer you to an alternate journal to submit the manuscript, along with the reviewers' report.

d. MAKE CHANGES AND SUBMIT TO A DIFFERENT JOURNAL

If you decide on trying a different journal, consider all the feedback you have previously received, so that your manuscript could be improved before submission.

Don't forget to tailor your manuscript to scope, and adjust details like the cover letter and referencing.

e. MAKE THE RECOMMENDED CHANGES AND RESUBMIT TO THE SAME JOURNAL

If you are keen to publish in a particular journal, this is what you were striving for.

Constructive criticism would lead to an improved version of your paper and good reviewers would expect to engage with you in a productive discussion.

To recap:

- ✓ There are always alternatives,
 - ✓ Do not ignore reviewers' comments.
 - ✓ A well-supported rebuttal will be considered,
- View rejection as a **learning opportunity**.